

AN ANALYTICAL STUDY ON Mr. G. RATHINAVEL AS A FREEDOM FIGHTER IN KARAIKAL

Dr. G. Aghalya

Head & Assistant Professor, Department of History, Bon Secours College for Women, Thanjavur, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: Dr. G. Aghalya, "An Analytical Study on Mr. G. Rathinavel as a Freedom Fighter in Karaikal", International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education, Volume 7, Issue 1, Page Number 56-58, 2021.

Copy Right: © IJMRME, 2021 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

Mr. Rathinavel was born in a good family at Neravy. His family members naturally had national sentiment. Like his family members he also had patriotic feelings by nature. When he was young, he wanted to do some social reforms for the society. It is important to note that he had naturally such feelings to do something good for our nation. He had an opportunity of serving the freedom fighters during his childhood. He usually went to school wearing Indian dress, ignoring English culture. From that time onwards he was eager to involve himself in the freedom struggle.

Introduction:

Many of the European countries vied with each other to establish their colonies on the Indian soil. The French were the last to appear on the political arena of India. Their object was to establish trade contacts with India, but having no support at their back, they were pushed to the background. French East India Company came into existence in 1664, and set up factories at Pondicherry, Karaikal, Mahe, Yanam and Chandranagore. Pondicherry was secured in 1674, from the ruler of Bijapur by Francisco Marttin.

His Participation in the Quit India Movement:

When in 9th August 1942 the Congress working committee was held at Bombay, it passed the famous Quit India resolution and this Quit India movement became extreme. The congress leader in all parts of India took part in this agitation following the doctrine of do or die of Gandhiji. Therefore the principal leaders of the congress party were arrested and imprisoned by the British police. All followers of congress party from Kashmir to Cape Comorine faced many difficulties and were even beatedn up by the polices of British Government. Against these atrocities various movements were started by the labourers, students and poor people. At the age of twenty, after seeing these atrocities he wrote the words Vellaiyane Velliearu on the walls of the main road in Nagapattinam during the night time and entered into Neravy, the French territory leaving the British India. So he escaped from the arrest of the police of British Government. This became the starting point of his long drawn struggle against the French.

His Participation in the French Parliament Election:

The method of French parliament deputation election was followed in two ways namely first and second. The first one called in French language premium list and the second Thesium list. In the first list, the French people retrieve French soldiers family and French renosance were there, and the Indians in the French India were included in the second list. According to this method on 15th October 1945 after the Second World War the French Parliament Deputation Election was held in Pondicherry. Mr. Jeevarathinam an advocate tried to abolish these two lists and competed in the election. So, Mr. Rathinavel supported Mr. Jeevarathinam and canvassed for him during the election. It is said that owing to the canvassing done by Mr. Rathinavel, Mr. Jeevatathinam got victory in the election. Mr. Jeevarathinam being elected became the member of the French parliament as desired by Mr. Rathinavel. After that for ten months period from 1945 to 1946 he continued to do social service and involved in conducting dramas for social reforms.

Arrival of Mr. Aruna Asaf Ali to Karaikal:

In 1946 Mr. ArunaAsaf Ali who absconded, came to Karaikal. After his arrival, the Quit India movement became very active in Pondicherry region day by day. Due to this the suppression of the French cirkar also became vigorous. On 9th August 1947 at Karaikal Rattai Kaithari Elainager Sangam, Didravid Kazhakam, Vevasayikal Sangam and Jawaharsangam conducted procession under the headship of Manavar congress (student's congress). This procession was banned by the French Cirkar. When the people violated the prohibitory ban orders of the French Cirkar. When the people violated the prohibitory ban orders of the French cirkar, the fighting occurred between them and the French police. The result was that the keraathikal placed in front of the Regional Executive Officer were broken into several pieces and the procession of the leaders was dissolved due to the lathi charge of the French police. In this fight some of the leaders were beaten up. One of them was Mr. Rathinavel's brothers.

In Karaikal region to join with Indian Union the Quit India movement became extreme and against the lathi charges various public meetings were held in the surrounding villages of Karaikal. At that time against the

meetings the member of upper house of French parliament sent the telegrams to Paris, it was supported by the Indian Government and Magazines. As a result Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru, then the prime minister of India, after having a talk with the French Government, concluded a treaty to conduct the public election at Pondicherry. Based on this treaty the Indians anticipated the resolution that whether the people in French India, would join with French Government or with Indian union.

Public Election:

On 24th October 1948 public election was held in Pondicherry. The representatives of both French Government and Indian Union came to Pondicherry as visitors. As in France the election was held at Pondicherry. Mr. Rathinavel nominated his brother to contest in the election. But the party which supported the people to join the French India with Indian Union failed. However Dr. N. V. Rajkumar who representatives of French Government and representative of Indian Union and Dr. Subrayan a representative, informed to the Indian Union that the method of this election was not proper. In this election the candidate who wanted to join the French India with Indian Union and their supporters were given lot of troubles by the supporters of the French cirkar Mr. Rathinavel was also one among them. His paddy fields at Neravy were ravaged and his cattle were stolen by the supporters of the French cirkar. Within few months about 365 violences took place in Pondicherry and Karaikal regions.

Arrival of Mr. Rajkumar to Pondicherry:

After coming to know about this violence, Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru sent Dr. N. V. Rajkumar, secretary of foreign department of Pondicherry to advise the freedom fighters to fight jointly but not separately Dr. N. V. Rajkumar was the supporter of integrating the French India with Indian Union. He combined all movements into one and named it merger congress. He appointed a president, vice-president, secretary and a treasurer for this congress. He also gave the power to all parties to elect nine members of executive committee. One of was Mr. Rathinavel.

Arrival of Mr. Rajkumar to Karaikal:

In 1949 Dr. N. V. Rajkumar who was the representative of Indian Government at New Delhi, arrived to Karaikal. He was cordially welcomed by the congress leaders and provided tea party in every commune. As the French Cirkar banned the public meetings in Karaikal Mr. Rathinavel conducted the meeting inside the building with Mr. N. V. Rajkumar. Therefore the French Cirkar induced its gunndas and attacked Mr. Rathinavel and others. His brother was being injured, admitted in the hospital. Mr. Rathinavel and his friend Mr. Muthu Vaithiyalingam Pillai were imprisoned. While he was in jail Mr. Rathinavel wrote on the atrocities and conspiracy of the French Cirkar against them in the jail on the paper through which he received parcel for breakfast and threw it out on the drainage. His friends collected these papers and published it for common people. After seeing this incident the French magistrate threatened him as to how the news went out from jail for the public.

Hoisting National Flag Opposite to Police Station:

In 1951 Mr. Rathinavel with his wife Smt. Soundaravally hoisted the Indian national flag opposite to police station at Neravy. Soon after the French cirkar removed the flag from there and sent away his family from Neravy. So he and his wife left Neravy and settled down at Thirumalairayanpattinam.

Split of Congress Party at Karaikal:

In Karaikal the congress party was split into two groups on account of the disputes among the members of the congress working party. Therefore Mr. Rathinavel worked separately. At that time he was helped by the All India Congress Committee and officers of Pondicherry consulate. He acted according to their guidelines. By the end of 1953 the Satyagraha movement reached its Zenith public meetings were held on the seashores with the support and leadership of Vedaranyam Vedarathinam Pillai, M.L.A., Periya Ayya Udaiyar and V. Subbaiah who was the head of the labourers and was expelled from Pondicherry region.

One day at Kothamangalam Mr. Rathinavel cautioned the French cirkar and delivered thundering speech against that cirkar to integrate the French India with Indian Union. This thundering speech provoked the French cirkar. As a result next day when he left to Nagapattinam the French police set fire to the boundless of straw which was kept behind his house, entered into his house and took all files, secret letters and telegrams sent by Sri. Kawal Singh. Besides they arrested his wife and took her to police station where they compelled her to say that her husband had lit the fire for the straw. When Mr. Rathinavel came back from Nagapattinam he was arrested and looked up in jail being accused of lighting the fire for straw, and his wife was released. At that time of condition of his wife and three year old daughter was miserable.

Arrival of Jijirekkar to Karaikal:

When the French consul of Pondicherry Mr. Jijirekkar came to know about the atrocity done to Mr. Rathinavel he came to karaikal to release Mr. Rathinavel. Upon his order the police of the French cirkar released him and did not take further action against him. Next day this news was informed to the congress leaders and administrations in Pondicherry and Delhi. According to their guidelines he left Neravy and settled down at

Nagapattinam situated in the Indian Union. Soon after his departure from Neravy his moveable properties were confiscated by the French cirkars.

As a result he gave up the policy of Ahimsha of Gandhiji and decided to follow the principles of Nethaji and became one of his extremists who kidnapped the French police to the Indian Union. Like them he also kidnapped a French police by name Mr. Arumugam with his weapons. When the French Government came to know about this it confiscated the weapons give to the police. The amount of allowance of rupees given to per police was raised to hundred rupees. To kidnap the police from French India, all keys of all outgates of Indian Union were given to him.

Hosting the Flag in the Office Administration:

Consulate General Mr. Sri Kawal Singh sent several telegrams to Mr. Rathinavel. He received the telegrams and according to that he hoisted the Indian National flag at the office of administration of Karaikal without knowing any one at midnight 12'0 clock and then he left French India to Indian Union, during the night time. Before the sun rise the French cirkar removed the flag. Moreover he planned to do various atrocities against the French cirkar. At that time the Army General Karlson who was working as a guideline for Indian Army and encamped at Keevalore sent C.I.D Inspector of police, Manorboy, C.I.D. Santhanam, Customes Superintendent, Jishnu to see him and informed through them not do any planned work now and should stop for some times because a treaty was made between India and France.

Freedom for French India:

As soon as he came to know about the freedom given to French india he stopped all his atrocities against the French cirkar. He informed the people that all the French decided to leave the French India and for that they were going to have election. At the same time he requested them to remain peaceful and not to indulge in any violence against the French cirkar. The election was also held at Pondicherry and hundred and eighty one person's cast their votes. Out of them hundred and seventy eight members cast their votes in supporting the French India to be merged with Indian Union and eight members did not like to join the French India with Indian Union.

When the Britishers decided to give freedom to Indians they gave dominion status first to Indians. Like that the French gave the de-factor rule to the Indians. On 1st November 1954 the French left India. The French Governor at Pondicherry Mon.Moonard handed over his duty to Mr. R.K. Nehru the foreign affairs secretary. Similarly Mon. Bussini a French administrator at Karaikal gave his duty to Mr. A.V. Loghanatha Mudaliyar who was a zilla collector in Indian Union. All French higher officers leaving the French India sailed on the ships to their mother country France. After that the Indian National flag was hoisted in the Governor's palace and other offices in Pondicherry and Karaikal region.

On 16th August 1962 Pondicherry obtained Dejur rule and the previous treaty was completely changed. After that Pondicherry region got full freedom. Mr. Rathinavel became more happy on hearing the news of freedom given to Pondicherry. Till date he is continuing to do his social, political and economic services the people.

References:

1. Primary Sources
 - Documents
 - Direct Interview
 - Letters from Articles
 - News Papers: Tamil & English
2. Secondary Sources:
 - Malleson G.B. ed, History of the French in India ,Gain Publishing House, New Delhi, 1986
 - Rajkumar N.V, Problem of India, Mukthi Press,Chandranagore,1951
 - Raja P A, Concise History of Pondicherry, All India Books Pondicherry, 1987.
 - Ramasamy A, History of Pondicherry, Sterling Publishers Private Limited, New Delhi 1987.
 - Ramasrinivasan R, Karaikal in Freedom Struggle Oualite offset, Pondicherry 1998.
 - Saroja Sundarajan, Glimpses of the History of Karaikal, Lalitha Publication, Madras, 1985.
 - Subbaiah V, Saga of Freedom of French India. New Century book house Private Limited, Madras, 1990.